

SoulSync: A Severity-Adaptive Multi-Modal Framework for Depression Screening Using BERT-Based NLP and PHQ-9 Clinical Scoring

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Abstract— SoulSync is a dual-pathway framework integrating BERT-embedded NLP with validated PHQ-9 clinical scoring. It introduces Severity-Adaptive Fusion (SAF), dynamically weighting modalities based on severity, heavy on clinical scores for severe cases, and NLP for mild cases. The BERT+Logistic Regression model achieved 95.5% accuracy on a Reddit test set. Analysis of 428 students identified worthlessness and concentration as dominant severity correlates. Lowering the NLP decision boundary to 0.40 improved recall to 0.980, effectively reducing false negatives critical in screening.

Keywords— Depression screening, NLP, severity-adaptive fusion, clinical decision support.

I. Introduction

Depression necessitates scalable screening, yet existing AI systems suffer from single-modality limits or data leakage. SoulSync integrates BERT-based NLP with validated PHQ-9 scoring. A Severity-Adaptive Fusion (SAF) gate dynamically weights modalities by severity, prioritizing clinical rigor for severe cases and NLP for hidden mild symptoms, while threshold optimization minimizes missed diagnoses [1].

II. Methodology

The system utilizes a primary PHQ-9 dataset (n=428 students) and a secondary Reddit dataset (1,000 posts). As illustrated in Fig. 1, the SoulSync framework consists of two parallel pathways feeding into the SAF gate: the NLP pathway (left) processes free text through preprocessing, tokenization, training, a language model, and embedding; the clinical pathway (right) computes the PHQ-9 total score, maps it to a severity band, and selects the corresponding $\alpha(s)$ weight. The SAF gate synthesizes both pathways into a composite Risk Label.

Figure 1. SoulSync system architecture. Left: NLP pathway (BERT+LR). Right: PHQ-9 clinical scoring pathway. Centre: SAF gate combining both modalities into a composite Risk Label.

Reddit Dataset Labeling. The 1,000-post sample is drawn from the publicly available *Depression: Reddit Dataset*

(*Cleaned*) [2], where labels are derived from subreddit membership (τ /depression vs. control communities)—a standard proxy strategy validated against PHQ-9 ground truth in prior work [3]. To bridge the linguistic gap between informal Reddit text and structured PHQ-9 responses, BERT’s bidirectional subword tokenization captures depressive semantics consistently across registers, enabling the same model to operate on both data modalities. **SAF Gate Weighting Function.** The severity-dependent weight $\alpha(s)$ is a piecewise-constant step function over five PHQ-9 severity bands (Table 1), not a continuous linear or sigmoid mapping. Each α value corresponds directly to the PHQ-9 reliability gradient established in clinical validation literature [3], making transitions discrete and clinically interpretable rather than learned. The composite risk score is:

$$\hat{y}_{SAF} = \alpha(s) \cdot S_{PHQ9} + (1 - \alpha(s)) \cdot P_{NLP}$$

where $S_{PHQ9} = \text{total}/27 \in [0, 1]$ and P_{NLP} is the BERT+LR depression probability. At None severity ($\alpha=0.35$), the NLP pathway receives 65% weight to surface hidden distress; at Severe ($\alpha=0.85$), the validated clinical instrument dominates, preventing a noisy NLP score from downgrading a critical risk flag.

Table 1. SAF Gate: PHQ-9 Severity Bands and α Values

PHQ-9 Score	Severity	α (Clinical)	$1-\alpha$ (NLP)
0–4	None	0.35	0.65
5–9	Mild	0.50	0.50
10–14	Moderate	0.60	0.40
15–19	Moderately Severe	0.70	0.30
20–27	Severe	0.85	0.15

III. Results and Discussion

Analysis of 428 students revealed 76.4% above the clinical threshold (≥ 10). Worthlessness ($r=0.76$) and concentration difficulty ($r=0.71$) were the strongest severity correlates ($p<0.001$), highlighting cognitive dominance in this South

Asian population. Table 2 compares all NLP configurations. The proposed BERT+LR model achieved the highest AUC (0.987) and precision (0.979), outperforming static embeddings.

Table 2. Reddit NLP Configurations – Full Comparison

Model	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F1	AUC
Logistic Regression	0.73	0.74	0.71	0.72	0.73
Random Forest	0.81	0.80	0.84	0.82	0.88
Support Vector Machine	0.70	0.80	0.53	0.63	0.77
W2V + Logistic Regression	0.72	0.77	0.62	0.69	0.70
W2V + Random Forest	0.79	0.74	0.88	0.81	0.86
W2V + Support Vector Machine	0.68	0.78	0.47	0.59	0.70
BERT + Random Forest	0.91	0.89	0.92	0.91	0.96
BERT + Support Vector Machine	0.94	0.90	1.00	0.95	0.98
BERT + LR	0.955	0.979	0.931	0.954	0.987

Sensitivity analysis showed lowering the decision threshold to 0.40 improved recall to 0.980, recovering five missed cases. The SAF gate (Table 3) demonstrates adaptive weighting: it prevents under-detection in mild cases (Case A) where NLP reveals hidden distress, and ensures clinical dominance in severe cases (Case C), consistent with the dual-pathway architecture shown in Fig. 1.

Table 3. SAF Gate – Representative Simulated User Scenarios

Case	PHQ-9	Band	S_{PHQ9}	P_{NLP}	α	Output Label
A	6	Mild	0.22	0.81	0.50	Moderate
B	14	Moderate	0.52	0.78	0.60	Moderate
C	22	Severe	0.81	0.94	0.85	Severe

IV. Conclusion

SoulSync resolves data leakage in PHQ-9 screening via a dual-pathway framework featuring a piecewise-constant, clinically grounded SAF gate. Analysis identified worthlessness and concentration difficulty as key severity correlates in a South Asian student population. The BERT+LR model achieved 0.987 AUC, with recall optimization addressing missed diagnoses. Future work includes multi-university validation, clinician-annotated Reddit labeling, and prospective clinical trials.

References

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